

LEARNING ENGLISH TENSES BY EASY WAYS**Elov Farrukh****Oygul Karimova***Bukhara region Gijduvan district Vocational School n-1**elovfarrukh86@gmail.com*

Annotation: It cannot be refuted the fact that the English language has become the supreme language around the world. Since English Language is treated as global language of business, it is necessary to develop the effective communication skills of English language. Effective communication skills of English language are necessary for the people of all professions. The concept of English 'verb tenses' is very important in establishing effective communication. Therefore, if one should maintain both ways of communication better, that is, speaking and writing.

Keywords: English language importance, Tenses, Types of tenses, time factors of usage tenses, usage of tenses.

INTRODUCTION

English Language is a considered as Global language, because most of the people in the world speak in English Language only. According to Professor David Crystal in his book titled "English Worldwide he mentioned that there were approximately 400 million native speakers of English. In addition, Crystal said that there were 400 million speakers of English as a second language. Furthermore, there were around 600 - 700 million English as a foreign language speakers. So, that's clearly over 1 billion people that could communicate in English to some extent. Those figures are also almost 11 years old, so we can surely say that those numbers of speakers have grown in the last decade. So, how in view of this we can estimate that there are definitely above 1.5 billion speakers of English globally [1].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the field of Education also English Language became essential and playing key role. Not only in India but also in many countries, children are asked to learn and taught and encouraged learn English as a second language.

It is most important to master over the tenses then only it is feasible to have good command on communication skills. Tenses are important to learn speaking and writing of English Language. The word, tense, has been derived from the Latin word '*Tempus*' which means time. In forming tenses it is most important to learn verbs. Basically a verb is a word which denotes three things action, position and possession of the subject. Ex: 1. Anu Radha *is teaching* Science. (Action) [2]

2. He *is* a teacher. (Position)
3. He *has* a scooter. (Possession)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Verbs are two types. They are main verbs and helping verbs.

Main Verbs

Root Verb Vo	Simple Present V1	Simple Past V2	Past Participle V3	Present Participle V4
Drink	drink / drinks	drank	drunk	drinking
Eat	eat/eats	ate	eaten	eating
Cook	cook/cooks	cooked	cooked	cooking
Go	go/goes	went	gone	going
Swim	swim/swims	swam	swum	swimming

Helping Verbs

Root Verb Vo	Simple Present V1	Simple Past V2	Past Participle V3	Present Participle V4
Be	is, am, are	was, were	been	being
Have	have / has	had	had	having
Do	do / does	did	done	doing

There are 24 helping verbs, out of 24 helping verbs twelve verbs are called Auxiliaries and remaining twelve are called Modal Auxiliaries.

Auxiliaries	Modal Auxiliaries
Be, is, am, are, was, were, have, has, had, do, does, did.	Will, would, shall, should, can, could, may might, must, ought, need, dare.

Here one thing should be observed that auxiliaries would be used as both main verbs and helping verbs. Ex: Rustam is teaching English. (Is used as helping Verb)

Rustam is a teacher. (Is used as main Verb)

Modal Auxiliaries will function always as helping verbs they never function as main verbs. In this case it should not be used two modal auxiliaries in one sentence.

Ex: You must and should attend my sister marriage. (wrong) Note: Either must or should anyone should be used.

Tenses

Mainly there are three tenses, past tense, present tense and the future tense. It is important to note that according to time it is said to be three tenses but according to verb forms we have only two tenses. They are Present and Past tense. The examples have been given below [3].

Root Verb Vo	Simple Present V1	Simple Past V2	Past Participle V3	Present Participle V4
Drink	drink / drinks	drank	drunk	drinking
Eat	eat/eats	ate	eaten	eating
Cook	cook/cooks	cooked	cooked	cooking

If we add any subject to V₁ it becomes simple present tense. Ex: 1. She cooks.

(She + V₁)

2. I drink. (I + V₁)

If we add any subject to V₂ it becomes simple past tense. Ex: 1. She cooked.

(She + V₂)

2. I drank. (I + V₂)

In the above sentences without adding any time indicators we got present and past tenses. But we cannot make future like because it requires time indicator.

Ex: He will eat a mango. ('Will' is time indicator in the sentence)

However there are three tenses according to time there is no doubt at all. Each of these tenses has four forms, they are: Simple, perfect, progressive or continuous, perfect progressive or perfect continuous.

Present Tense

- 1.Simple Present Tense
- 2.Present Perfect Tense
- 3.Present Continuous Tense
- 4.Present Perfect Continuous Tense

Past Tense

- 1.Simple Past Tense
- 2.Past Perfect Tense
- 3.Past Continuous Tense
- 4.Past Perfect Continuous Tense

Future Tense

- 1.Simple Future Tense
- 2.Future Perfect Tense
- 3.Future Continuous Tense
- 4.Future Perfect Continuous Tense

For the convenience of the learners it is formed in a easy method to understand the differentiation among tenses as simple once, perfect once, continuous once, perfect continuous once.

Simple Tenses

S.No	Simple Tenses	Name of the Tense	Syntax or Structure of Sentence
1.	I go to school.	Simple Present Tense	Subject + V1 + Object
2.	I went to school.	Simple Past Tense	Subject + V2 + Object
3.	I shall go to school.	Simple Future Tense	Subject + V0 + Object

Perfect Tenses

S.No	Perfect Tenses	Name of the Tense	Syntax or Structure of Sentence
4.	I have gone to school.	Present Perfect Tense	Subject + have / has + V3 + Object
5.	I had gone to school.	Past Perfect Tense	Subject + had + V3 + Object

6.	I shall have gone to school.	Future Perfect Tense	Subject + will / shall + V3 + Object
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Simple present tense is used to tell about the actions which would take place now, regularly takes place present time or in short period. The time indicators are every day, every month, always, usually, often, sometimes, occasionally, rarely and never.

Ex:

1. She + *cooks* + food every day. (cook + s) Sub + V1 + Object

2. Kasim + *goes* + to college every day. (go + es) Sub + V1 + Object

Note: While writing simple present tense if the subject is third person singular then we have to add 's' or 'es' to the verb form [5].

Simple Past Tense

Simple past tense is used to talk about a **completed action** in the past. The simple past is the basic form of past tense in English. It is used to express the past events when they took place in the past exactly and indefinitely.

1. She + *cooked* + rice yesterday. Sub + V2 + Object

2. I + *went* + to market one hour ago. Sub + V2 + Object

Usage of Simple Past Tense

- ❖ It is used to tell about past incidents which took place in the past.
- ❖ It is used with another simple past tense.

Simple Future Tense

Simple future tense is used to express a thing which would take place in future in the sense later than now. It expresses the speaker's opinions, assumptions and speculations about future.

1. She + *will* + *cook* + Biryani tomorrow. Sub + will / shall + V0 + Object.

2. I + *shall* + *go* + to market next Sunday.

Sub + will / shall + V0 + Object.

Future time indicators are tomorrow, next week, next year etc.

Present Continuous Tense is used to denote an action in progress at the time of speaking and an action that will take place in the near future.

Ex.

- 1.They + are + watching + match.Sub + is/am/are + V4 + Obj.
- 2.Lalitha is writing a letter.

Past Continuous Tense is used to describe an action going on in the past, when two actions took place in the past at the same time; both the actions are described in the past continuous. Simultaneously when two actions took place in the past while one action was going on another action took place. Then the action which was going on for that past continuous and for another simple past is used.

Ex.

- 1.They + were + making + kites.Sub + was/were + V4 + Obj.
- 2.While I was taking bath my mobile rang.

CONCLUSION

Learning Tenses is most important for Second Language learners and Non-native Speakers because learning tenses fetch them knowledge of understanding the sentences or sentence construction and trying to comprehend the meaning of sentences or paragraphs whenever they study English Language Books. Without learning or knowing proper or perfect usage of tenses no one can become good learner or speaker. It is multipurpose, learning tenses for Second Language learners as well as Non-native Speakers to overcome their phobia of English fear and terror. Once they are mastered in learning tenses along with usage of time factor they can read and understand English language and other subjects too. Simultaneously they can improve their communication skills also.

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